

INTER REGIONAL DISPARITY OF SOCIO - ECONOMIC VARIABLES OF MEMBERS OF SHGS IN MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

Self Help Groups have greater influence on socio - economic variables of its members, it may be towards equity or disparity. Educational expenditure is increasing towards equality due to SHGs. This is good sign of socio - economic development of society due to SHGs. But medical expenditure and entertainment expenditure are increasing with disparity due to SHGs is main social concern. Thus, to generalize this successful movement in entire nation should have proper policy measures and efficient implementation of the same.

The concept of SHGs is very significant for poor people, especially the rural women those who don't have any alternative for living. The empowerment of women through SHG would lead to benefit not only to the individual women and women groups but also for their families and community through collective action for development. (Pawar S.A., 2019) These groups have a common perception of need and impulse towards collective action. SHGs have greater influence on socio - economic variables of its members, it may be towards equity or disparity. Thus, in this paper researcher has tried to focus on inter regional disparity of socio - economic variable due to SHGs in Maharashtra.

1. Objectives:

1. To study the inter-regional disparity of education expenditure of members of SHGs in Maharashtra.
2. To study the inter-regional disparity of medical expenditure of members of SHGs in Maharashtra.
3. To study the inter-regional disparity of entertainment expenditure of members of SHGs in Maharashtra.

4. To compare disparity of socio - economic variables before and after joining SHGs in Maharashtra.
5. To suggest suggestions for more efficiency and more equity of economic variables of SHGs in Maharashtra.

2. Hypothesis of the Study:

1. Due to SHGs, education expenditure of members of SHGs has increased towards equality.
2. Due to SHGs, medical expenditure of members of SHGs has increased towards equality.
3. Due to SHGs, entertainment expenditure of members of SHGs has increased towards equality.

3. Research Methodology

The present study purely depends on primary data. Primary data was collected through survey method by administering separate structured questionnaires to the concerned set of respondent. The study area was Maharashtra. The Stratified Random Sampling Method was selected by the researcher to select responsible. This sampling method was selected by researcher, because the study area was very vast i.e. Maharashtra state. To select the samples five administrative regions of Maharashtra i.e. Western Maharashtra, Marathwada, Konkan, Vidharbh and North Maharashtra had been selected for the study. From every administrative regions one district (having large number of SHGs) had been selected i.e. from Westron Maharashtra Solapur, from Marathwada Nanded district, from Vidharbh Nagpur district, from North Maharashtra Nasik district, from Konkan Thane district have selected. From every district two blocks had been selected for the study. Thus, from each block five Villages had been selected for collecting the primary data. From five Villages 100 SHG members i.e. from every Villages two SHGs.(20 SHG members) had been selected, means total 5 regions*200 SHGs members =1000 sample size of the respondents had been selected for the study.

4. Education Expenditure of SHGs Members

Education expenditure of the person is most influencing factor of performance. It is investment in human capital Table No. 01 shows inter regional disparity of family education expenditure of SHGs members before and after joining SHGs in Maharashtra. Table no. 01 indicates that in all three regional area's Gini Coefficient of members' education expenditure

before joining SHGs was more than after joining SHGs, except North Maharashtra and Marathwada, average Gini's coefficient had declining trend. Conclusion is after membership of SHGs, members' education expenditure is increased more towards equality, because average Gini Coefficient of income before joining SHGs was 0.264 and it was 0.254 after joining SHGs.

Table No. 01: Inter Regional Disparity of Education Expenditure before and after

Joining SHGs			
Sr. No.	Area	Before Joining SHG (Value of Gini Coefficient)	After Joining SHG (Value of Gini Coefficient)
1	North Maharashtra	0.2672	0.2537
2	Vidharbha	0.1984	0.2599
3	West Maharashtra	0.1171	0.1472
4	Kokan	0.2079	0.2439
5	Marathwada	0.5281	0.3656
Average		0.264	0.254

Source: Field Survey

Note: GC= Gini Coefficient

5. Medical Expenditure of SHGs Members

Medical expenditure of households refers to the total financial cost incurred by a household on healthcare services and products. Average healthcare expenditure in India was around 18 % (NSSO, 2011-12). It is going Out of Pocket of the Indian households. It influences households significantly. Table No. 02 shows inter regional disparity of family healthcare expenses of SHGs members before and after joining SHGs in Maharashtra. This table indicates that in all three regional area's Gini Coefficient of medical expenditure before joining SHGs was less than after joining SHGs, except Vidarbha and Marathwada. Average Gini's coefficient increased. On the basis of this analysis, we conclude that after membership of SHGs medical expenditure is increased more towards disparity, because average Gini Coefficient of saving before joining SHGs was 0.248 and it was 0.269 after joining SHGs.

Table No. 02: Inter Regional Disparity of Family Medical Expenditure before and after Joining SHGs

Sr. No.	Area	Before SHG (Value of Gini Coefficient)	Joining Gini	After SHG (Value of Gini Coefficient)
1	North Maharashtra	0.2769		0.3472
2	Vidharbha	0.1954		0.1944
3	West Maharashtra	0.0702		0.0834
4	Kokan	0.1987		0.2666
5	Marathwada	0.5013		0.4517
	Average	0.248		0.269

Source: *Field Survey*Note: GC= *Gini Coefficient***6. Entertainment Expenditure SHGs Members**

Entertainment expenditure of the person is discretionary expenditure, which consist costs for leisure and pastimes might be part of a household's regular expenditures. Table No. 03 shows inter regional disparity of entertainment expenditure of SHGs members before and after joining SHGs in Maharashtra. This table indicates that in all four regional areas Gini Coefficient of Living expenditure before joining SHGs was less than after joining SHGs, Gini's coefficient increased, except North Maharashtra. On the basis of this analysis we conclude that after membership of SHGs entertainment expenditure is decreased more towards disparity, because average Gini Coefficient of Living expenditure before joining SHGs was 0.224 and it was 0.235 after joining SHGs.

Table No. 03: Inter Regional Disparity of Entertainment Expenditure before and after Joining SHGs

Sr. No.	Area	Before SHG (Value of Gini Coefficient)	Joining Gini	After Joining SHG (Value of Gini Coefficient)
1	North Maharashtra	0.3090		0.2441
2	Vidharbha	0.1742		0.1942
3	West Maharashtra	0.1048		0.1226
4	Kokan	0.2329		0.3119
5	Marathwada	0.3009		0.3042
	Average	0.224		0.235

Source: *Field Work*Note: GC= *Gini Coefficient*

07. Major Findings:

1. It is concluded that after membership of SHGs, members' education expenditure is increased more towards equality, because average Gini Coefficient of income before joining SHGs was 0.264 and it was 0.254 after joining SHGs.
2. It is concluded that after membership of SHGs, medical expenditure is increased more towards disparity, because average Gini Coefficient of saving before joining SHGs was 0.248 and it was 0.269 after joining SHGs.
3. It concludes that after membership of SHGs, entertainment expenditure is decreased more towards disparity, because average Gini Coefficient of Living expenditure before joining SHGs was 0.224 and it was 0.235 after joining SHGs.

8. Major Suggestions

1. Medical expenditure by members from SHGs is increasing towards disparity, thus Government should provide all medical facilities at minimum charges.
2. Government should have full control on medical hospital. Private hospitals should have minimum approval and access.
3. NGOs and Trusts should come up to provide medicinal facilities.
4. Bank's participation in SHG's movement is limited, therefore banks should increase their participation in provision of educational and healthcare facilities.
5. State and Central Government should take initiatives to avail various educational schemes to SHG members.
6. Government should give subsidy on healthcare and educational facilities to the members of SHGs.
7. Government should provide medical insurance to the members of SHGs to cover medicinal expenses.

9. Conclusion

On basis of above analysis researcher came to conclude that SHGs have positive impact on socio – economic variables of SHGs members. Education expenditure is increasing towards equality and entertainment expenditure is increasing towards disparity due to SHGs. This is good sign of socio - economic development of society due to SHGs. But the medical expenditure is increasing towards disparity, it is sign of social concern. But successful movement of SHGs is limited up to certain areas of the nation. It should be generalize in entire nation. It will bring socio-economic sustainability in society. Thus, to generalize this

successful movement in entire nation Government should provide subsidy to SHGs, should reduce the rate of interest on loan, should available sufficient healthcare facilities for marginal factors on subsidized and minimum rates, banks should provide sufficient implement educational and medicinal schemes to support to SHGs, Government should frame various educational schemes for members of SHGs etc. Thus, efficient and self reliable SHGS will help in socio - economic development of nation, in increase socio-economic welfare of the society. For this purpose, Government should have proper policy measures and efficient implementation of the same.

10. Bibliography

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